

Bridge and Bridgeless Single Stage Conversion for EV Charging

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ABSTRACT

The rapid growth of electric vehicles (EVs) necessitates the development of high-efficiency, compact, and intelligent battery charging systems. This paper proposes a bridge-based single-stage EV battery charger that integrates power factor correction (PFC) and DC–DC conversion into a unified topology. The system employs a full-bridge converter-controlled pulse-width modulation (PWM) techniques to regulate output voltage and current while ensuring high conversion efficiency. To further improve performance, soft-switching is achieved through resonant control strategies, such as zero-voltage switching (ZVS), which significantly reduces switching losses and electromagnetic interference (EMI).

Simulation results obtained using MATLAB/Simulink validate the effectiveness of the proposed charger in achieving high efficiency, improved power quality, and precise regulation. The developed bridge single-stage EV charging system provides a promising solution for modern fast-charging applications, combining compact design with enhanced electrical performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancement of electric mobility necessitates the development of Power electronic interfaces that balance efficiency, power density, and cost-effectiveness are required due to the quick development of electric mobility [1]. By analyzing the trade-offs between conventional diode bridge rectifiers and new bridgeless topologies, current research aims to optimize AC/DC conversion stages [2]. Because of their ability to lower conduction losses and the total number of components, bridgeless architectures are becoming more and more popular. This improves system efficiency in front-end power factor correction [2]. Additionally, a route to high power density and dependable V2G functionality is provided by integrating bidirectional dual-active-bridge converters and soft-switching techniques in single-stage systems [3]. These configurations greatly reduce conduction losses and enhance thermal management throughout the conversion process by doing away with the traditional diode bridge rectifier[3] However, in order to manage the increased number of switching devices, these bridgeless designs frequently require more complex gate-drive circuitry and sophisticated control algorithms[4]. Current research frequently uses sophisticated control strategies, like space vector modulation or open-loop PFC techniques, to maintain sinusoidal current waveforms in order to address these issues [5]. Concurrently, these single-stage systems are further optimized by the use of wide-bandgap semiconductor devices, such as silicon carbide, which allow for higher switching frequencies that effectively reduce the volume of passive[5,6]. The development of scalable, modular charging infrastructure that supports a variety of vehicle-to-grid (V2G) power flow requirements depends on these advancements in switching speed and power density [6,7]

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Author(s) (Year)	Current Status & Gap	Required Action
R. Kumar and B. Singh (2024)	A bridgeless PFC-based EV battery charger was presented to improve efficiency and reduce harmonics. However, a detailed comparison with conventional bridge converters was not discussed.	Carry out a comparative study between bridge and bridgeless topologies and evaluate their performance under different operating conditions.
H. Li, Y. Zhang, and X. He (2024)	A bridgeless single-stage converter for EV charging was developed with suitable control methods. The effect of varying battery conditions and practical implementation aspects received limited attention.	Examine the converter performance for different load conditions and verify the results through simulation and experimental studies.
P. Kumar, S. Jain, and V. Agarwal (2024)	A high-efficiency bridgeless AC–DC converter with power factor correction was proposed. The study provides limited information on thermal performance and long-term operation.	Investigate thermal characteristics and reliability to improve the practical suitability of the converter.
S. Haghbin, S. Lundmark, M. Alakula, and O. Carlson (2013)	Different grid-connected battery charging approaches were reviewed and a new solution was introduced. Less emphasis was placed on single-power-conversion bridgeless structures.	Explore advanced single-stage bridgeless configurations for improving efficiency and reducing circuit complexity.
M. Yilmaz and P. T. Krein (2013)	Various charger topologies and charging infrastructures for electric vehicles were reviewed. Detailed analysis of individual converter configurations was not provided.	Compare recent converter topologies and identify suitable designs for efficient EV charging applications.
A. Khaligh and S. Dusmez (2012)	Conductive and inductive charging methods for plug-in electric vehicles were analyzed. Further improvements in AC–DC conversion efficiency and harmonic reduction are still needed.	Develop converter topologies that offer better efficiency and improved power quality.

3. PROBLEM STATEMENT

- Low efficiency of conventional EV chargers
- Bulky and unreliable DC-link capacitors
- High conduction and switching losses

3.1 OBJECTIVES

- Develop and design the a bridgeless single-stage AC–DC converter for EV battery charging with high efficiency
- Eliminate the bridge diode rectifier
- Combine power factor correction (PFC) and DC–DC conversion in a single stage and multistage. Improve efficiency by transferring input energy directly to the battery without an intermediate energy buffer.

4.0 METHODOLOGY

The proposed Bridge Single Power Conversion EV Battery Charging system converts single-phase AC supply into regulated DC power for EV battery charging. A full-bridge rectifier converts AC to DC, and a boost converter is used to regulate and increase the output voltage. High-frequency switching improves power factor, reduces harmonic distortion, and maintains stable output voltage. The output capacitor filters ripple and supplies smooth DC power to the battery. The entire system is modeled and analyzed in MATLAB/Simulink to evaluate parameters such as voltage, current, duty cycle, ripple, power factor, and efficiency.

Design Parameters and Theoretical Calculations

Parameters	Values
Input voltage	226.9V
Input current	30A
Ref output voltage	284.6V
Ref output current	28.46A
Switching Frq	25KHz

Table 1: Design Parameters and Theoretical Calculations values

The design parameters of the proposed bridge-based single power conversion EV battery charger are presented. These parameter values are selected based on the charging requirements of the EV battery, the characteristics of the utility supply, converter design constraints, and the need to achieve high efficiency with improved power quality. The input voltage is chosen as 226.9 V AC because it closely represents the standard single-phase utility supply voltage of 230 V AC commonly available in residential and commercial charging stations. Designing the converter for this voltage ensures compatibility with existing power distribution systems without requiring additional voltage conversion equipment. The corresponding peak voltage is approximately 320 V, which serves as the input to the rectification and boost conversion stages. The input current is selected as 30 A to provide sufficient charging power for the EV battery. This current level enables the charger to deliver approximately 6.8 kW of power, which is suitable for medium-power EV charging applications. The selected value also allows the performance of the converter to be evaluated under practical operating conditions.

The reference output voltage is chosen as 284.6 V based on the voltage requirement of the battery pack used in the study. Since the converter operates as a boost converter, the output voltage must be high .

Theoretical values Calculation:

1. Input Voltage (AC):

$$V_{in} = 226.92$$

$$V_{peak} = \sqrt{2} \times 226.9 = 320V$$

$$f = 50 \text{ Hz}$$

2. Input power = $P_{in} = V_{in} \times I_{in} \times PF$

$$= 226.9 \times 30$$

$$= 6807$$

$$P_{in} = 6.8 \text{ KW}$$

3. Duty cycle $D = 1 - V_{in}/V_o$

$$D = 1 - \frac{226.9}{284.6}$$

$$D = 1 - 0.797 \approx 0.20$$

$$\text{Duty cycle} \approx 0.2 \text{ (20\%)}$$

4. Inductor (L)

$$L = \frac{V_{in} \cdot D}{f_s \cdot \Delta I_L}$$

Assume:

$$\text{Switching frequency} = 25000 \text{ Hz}$$

$$\text{Ripple current } \Delta I_L = 20\% I_{in}$$

$$\Delta I = I_{max} - I_{min}$$

$$\text{Maximum current } I_{max} = 32 \text{ A}$$

$$\text{Minimum current } I_{min} = 26 \text{ A}$$

$$\Delta I = 32 - 26 = 6 \text{ A}$$

$$\text{Ripple current } \Delta I_L = 20\% I_{in}$$

$$\bullet \Delta I_L = 0.2 \times 30.8 = \mathbf{6.1 \text{ A}}$$

Ripple CURRENT percentage

find average current:

$$I_{avg} = \frac{I_{max} + I_{min}}{2}$$

$$I_{avg} = \frac{32 + 26}{2} = 29 \text{ A}$$

$$\text{Percentage r} \quad \% \text{Ripple current} = \frac{\Delta I}{I_{avg}} \times 100$$

$$= \frac{6}{29} \times 100$$

$$= 20\%$$

$$\text{Now:} \quad L = \frac{226.9 \times 0.2}{25000 \times 6.1} \quad \mathbf{L = 3 \text{ m H}}$$

5. DC link Capacitor

$$C = \frac{I_o \cdot D}{f_s \cdot V_{ripple}}$$

Assume:

- Switching frequency = 25 000Hz

$$C = \frac{28.46 \cdot 0.2}{25000 \cdot 10}$$

Capacitor \approx 2200 μ F

$$V_{max} \approx 285V$$

$$V_{min} \approx 275V$$

$$\text{Voltage Ripple} = V_{max} - V_{min}$$

$$V_{ripple} = 285 - 275 = 10V$$

$$\% \text{Voltage ripple} = \frac{V_{ripple}}{V_{dc}} \times 100$$

$$= \frac{10}{284.6} \times 100 = 3.5\%$$

6. Load Resistance

$$R = \frac{v_o}{I_o} = \frac{283.4}{28.46} \quad R = 10 \Omega$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Input power} &= P_{in} = V_{in} \times I_{in} \times PF \\ &= 226.9 \times 30 \\ &= 6807 \end{aligned}$$

9. Output Power = Pout = Vo x Io

$$\begin{aligned} P_{out} &= 284.6 \times 28.46 \\ P_{out} &= 8098W \end{aligned}$$

7. Output Voltage

$$V_o = \frac{V_{in}}{1 - D}$$

$$V_o = \frac{226.9}{1 - 0.2}$$

$$= 282.5V$$

10. Efficiency

$$\eta = \frac{P_{in}}{P_{out}} \times 100$$

$$\eta = \frac{6807}{8098} \times 100$$

$$\eta = 86.4\%$$

Figure 1: Circuit diagram of bridge single power conversion EV battery charging

Circuit Description and Operation of Bridge Single Power Conversion EV Battery Charge

This proposed bridge single power conversion EV battery charger is designed to convert single-phase AC power into a regulated DC output for charging an electric vehicle battery. The charger consists of a bridge rectifier, boost converter, PWM controller, output capacitor, and battery load. The overall system provides efficient power conversion while maintaining stable charging voltage and current. The charging process begins with a 230 V, 50 Hz single-phase AC supply. This AC voltage is applied to the bridge rectifier stage, which consists of four diodes (D1–D4). The bridge rectifier converts the alternating voltage into a pulsating DC voltage by utilizing both positive and negative half-cycles of the AC waveform. During the positive half-cycle, diodes D1 and D4 conduct, while during the negative half-cycle, diodes D2 and D3 conduct. As a result, a full-wave rectified voltage is obtained at the output of the rectifier. The rectified voltage is then supplied to the boost converter. The boost converter consists of an inductor (L), power switch (MOSFET), boost diode (D), and output capacitor (C). This stage is responsible for increasing and regulating the DC voltage according to the charging requirements of the EV battery. When the MOSFET switch is turned ON, current flows through the inductor and energy is stored in the form of a magnetic field. During this interval, the boost diode remains reverse biased, preventing current flow to the output side. As the switch remains ON, the inductor current gradually increases and stores energy.

3 Design Parameters and Theoretical Calculations

Parameters	Values
Input voltage	230V
Input current	4.35A
Ref output voltage	500V
Ref output current	6.5A
Switching Frq	50KHz

Table 2: Design Parameters and Theoretical Calculations values

The proposed bridgeless single power conversion EV battery charger is designed to operate from a standard single-phase AC supply voltage of 230 V, which is readily available in most residential and commercial electrical networks. The selection of this input voltage ensures easy integration with the existing utility infrastructure and eliminates the requirement for additional input conditioning stages, thereby reducing system complexity and cost. Since 230 V is the commonly adopted mains voltage in many countries, the charger can be conveniently deployed for practical electric vehicle charging applications. The input current is maintained at 4.35 A, which is determined according to the power rating of the converter and the charging requirements of the battery. This current level enables adequate power transfer from the grid while maintaining stable operation and preventing excessive loading of the supply network. Furthermore, limiting the input current contributes to improved safety, reduced conduction losses, and enhanced reliability of the overall charging system.

The converter is designed to regulate the output voltage at 500 V DC, which serves as the reference voltage required for charging high-voltage electric vehicle battery packs. A regulated output voltage is essential for ensuring safe and efficient charging, as fluctuations in voltage may adversely affect battery performance and lifespan. By maintaining a constant DC output voltage, the charger provides a stable energy source to the battery and prevents overvoltage conditions that could lead to overheating or degradation of battery cells. The reference output current is selected as 6.5 A to deliver the required charging power while maintaining controlled charging characteristics. This charging current is chosen to achieve an appropriate balance between charging speed and battery health. Excessively high charging currents may increase battery temperature and accelerate aging, whereas lower currents may result in prolonged charging times. Therefore, the selected current value ensures efficient energy transfer, minimizes thermal stress, and contributes to extending the service life of the battery.

Theoretical values Calculation:

1. Input Voltage (AC):

$$V_{in} = 230$$

Peak Voltage:

$$V_{peak} = \sqrt{2} \times 230 = 325V$$

$$f = 50 \text{ Hz}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{2. Input power} = P_{in} &= V_{in} \times I_{in} \times PF \\ &= 230 \times 4.35 \\ &= 1000.5 \end{aligned}$$

$$V_{max} \approx 285V$$

$$V_{min} \approx 275V$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Voltage Ripple} &= V_{max} - V_{min} \\ V_{ripple} &= 285 - 275 = 10V \end{aligned}$$

$$\% \text{Voltage ripple} = \frac{V_{ripple}}{V_{dc}} \times 100$$

$$= \frac{10}{284.6} \times 100$$

$$= 3.5\%$$

3. DUTY CYCLE

We calculate the Duty Cycle D

$$D = 1 - \frac{220}{500} = 0.56$$

4. Inductor (L)

$$L = \frac{V_{in} \cdot D}{f_s \cdot \Delta I_L}$$

Switching frequency = 50KHz

Assume:

• Switching frequency = 50000Hz (50KHz)

• Ripple current $\Delta I_L = 20\% I_{in}$

$$\Delta I_L = 0.2 \times 4.35 = 0.87A$$

Now:

$$L = \frac{230 \times 0.5}{50000 \times 0.87}$$

$$L = 2.75 \text{ mH} = 3 \text{ mH}$$

6. Load Resistance

$$R = \frac{V_o}{I_o}$$

$$= \frac{(500) \text{ V}}{6.58}$$

$$R = 76 \Omega$$

7. Output Voltage

$$V_o = \frac{V_{in}}{1 - D}$$

$$V_o = \frac{220}{1 - 0.56}$$

$$V_o = 500V$$

8. Output Current

$$I_o = \frac{282.5}{76}$$

$$I_o = 6.582A$$

EFFICIENCY

$$\eta = P_{in}/P_{out} \times 100$$

$$\eta = 97.25$$

5. DC link Capacitor

$$C = \frac{I_o \cdot D}{f_s \cdot V_{ripple}}$$

Assume:

*Switching frequency = 50000Hz

$$C = \frac{6.5 \cdot 0.5}{50000 \cdot 10}$$

Capacitor $\approx 220\mu\text{F}$

$$\Delta I = I_{max} - I_{min}$$

Maximum current $I_{max} \approx 32 \text{ A}$

Minimum current $I_{min} \approx 26 \text{ A}$

$$\Delta I = 32 - 26 = 6A$$

Ripple CURRENT percentage
find average current:

$$I_{avg} = \frac{I_{max} + I_{min}}{2}$$

$$I_{avg} = \frac{32 + 26}{2} = 29 \text{ A}$$

Percentage ripple:

$$\% \text{Ripple current} = \frac{\Delta I}{I_{avg}} \times 100$$

$$= \frac{6}{29} \times 100$$

$$= 20\%$$

Figure 2: Circuit diagram of bridgeless single power conversion EV battery charging

Circuit Description and Operation of Bridge Single Power Conversion EV Battery Charger

The proposed bridge single power conversion EV battery charger converts the single-phase AC supply into a regulated DC output required for charging an electric vehicle battery. The circuit consists of a full-bridge rectifier, boost converter, PWM controller, output capacitor, and battery load. These components work together to achieve efficient power conversion and stable charging operation.

A single-phase AC supply of 230 V, 50 Hz is applied to the input of the charger. The bridge rectifier, formed by four diodes (D1–D4), converts the AC voltage into a pulsating DC voltage by utilizing both positive and negative half-cycles of the input waveform. This provides a unidirectional current suitable for further processing. The rectified voltage is then supplied to the boost converter, which consists of an inductor, MOSFET switch, boost diode, and output capacitor. The boost converter increases the DC voltage to the level required for battery charging.

When the switch is turned ON, energy is stored in the inductor, and when the switch is turned OFF, the stored energy is transferred to the output through the diode. In this way, a higher output voltage is obtained. The MOSFET is controlled using pulse width modulation (PWM) operating at a switching frequency of 25 kHz. By adjusting the duty cycle, the converter maintains the desired output voltage and charging current. The output capacitor filters the switching ripple and provides a smooth DC voltage to the battery.

Finally, the regulated DC power is supplied to the EV battery for charging. The overall system provides reliable operation, good voltage regulation, and efficient energy transfer.

5. SIMULATION RESULT

Proposed simulation model of closed loop-controlled AC-DC converter for battery charging of light electric vehicle's is designed in MATLAB/Simulink. illustrates the MATLAB/Simulink model developed for the proposed closed-loop AC–DC converter used for charging a light electric vehicle battery. The model includes the power conversion circuit along with a feedback control system. The controller compares the actual output with the reference value and accordingly produces the switching pulses required for proper converter operation. This control action helps maintain the desired charging voltage and current throughout the charging process. From the obtained waveforms, it can be observed that the converter provides a well-regulated output with low ripple content and satisfactory efficiency. The simulation results indicate that the proposed converter is capable of delivering reliable and stable performance for battery charging applications.

As Show Below Figure:

BRIDGE SINGLE POWER CONVERSION OF EV BATTERY CHARGING

Figure 3: Simulink Diagram of Bridge single power Conversion EV battery charging

Figure 4: Output Voltage of the System with Bridge

Figure 5: Output current of the System with Bridge is 30

BRIDGELESS SINGLE POWER CONVERSION OF EV BATTERY CHARGING

Figure 7: Simulation diagram of Bridgeless single power conversion of Ev battery Charging

Figure5:Output Voltage of the System with Bridgeless is 500V

IV. CONCLUSION

The Proposed model is successfully designed and The comparative analysis of bridge and bridgeless single power conversion EV battery chargers shows that both configurations are capable of supplying the required DC power for charging electric vehicle batteries. The conventional bridge converter offers a simple and reliable design, but the presence of the diode bridge results in additional conduction losses and slightly lower efficiency. On the other hand, the bridgeless topology eliminates these losses by reducing the number of conducting devices, thereby improving efficiency, power factor, and overall performance while reducing thermal stress and harmonic distortion. Simulation and theoretical results indicate that the bridgeless converter delivers better energy utilization and stable output characteristics, making it a more suitable and efficient solution for modern electric vehicle charging applications.

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